

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARL LECHBEN O. GAPUTAN, MPA, LPT

Assistant Professor I

Camiguin Polytechnic State College

nebhcel@gmail.com

“JOB SATISFACTION”

Job satisfaction or contentment is a belief that there are many personal characteristics that affects how an employee or worker perceives a particular job. Supervisors or managers, when making assessments, must consider these personal factors, while also examining the characteristics of the work environment, as both are equally important.

Comprehensive review of empirical studies of job satisfaction or contentment by Edwin A. Locke reveals that there are seven working conditions that lead to job satisfaction or contentment. These are, first, mentally challenging work which the individual can cope successfully; second, personal interest in the work itself; third, rewards for performance in line with personal aspirations that are just and understood; fourth, work which is not too tiring physically; fifth, working conditions which are compatible with the individual's physical needs and work goal; sixth, high self-esteem on the part of the employee; and seventh, help in attaining interesting work, pay, promotions and in minimizing role conflict and ambiguity.

When a job's total content is too large and too complex for any individual to handle competently, frustration and low job satisfaction will occur. Therefore, specialization of jobs is related to job satisfaction or contentment. The narrower the scope of the job, the fewer the number of operations, job satisfaction or contentment of the employees will be high.

Job satisfaction or contentment and morale are influenced by the organization's structural characteristics and by the physical characteristics of the job. Frustration and discontent, conflict and alienation are inevitable in dissatisfying jobs; these affects the actions and attitudes of the individual. Satisfaction and performance are related too. Dissatisfaction also exists. The lack of well-defined structure of reporting, relationships and authority can lead to a great deal of uncertainty and ambiguity, hence, anxiety. Responsibilities shift with the requirements of new problems and assignments. In some cases, events and projects may move so quickly that responsibilities are not well communicated.

Based on the book written by Pacita A. Abasolo, there are certain factors within an organization that affects the state of satisfaction of employees. Failure of employees and managers to perform their work with maximum effectiveness may be caused by mere lack of knowledge of the results expected of them. When the organization's objectives are made known to both employees and managers, this will serve as a guide in the use of available resources for maximum advantage.

It has also been said that working conditions determine the satisfaction of an employee such as lighting, temperature, humidity, noise, dust, radiation, other health hazards, and nature of the work like hours of work, skills required, physical effort, and efforts exerted mentally.

